

Recent Investigations of Indian Medicinal Plant Products*

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During the last five years, our main interest of work centred round the Indian medicinal plant products particularly in relation to cardiovascular agents and I propose to restrict myself to this area alone. The overall objective of the investigation was primarily, to develop a hypotensive drug from indigenous sources other than *Rauwolfia* alkaloids and to attempt to understand the structure-activity relationships, if any, besides research for other plant products of structural and biogenetic interest, a pursuit inherent in plant chemists.

I. Studies on *Alangium lamarckii* Thw. Syn. *A. sylvifolium* (Linn. f.) Wang.

In search of hypotensive principle from indigenous natural sources other than *Rauwolfia*^{1, 2}, we chose *Alangium lamarckii* Thw., a widely distributed^{3, 4} spine-scented shrub or small tree of vigorous growth for investigation. Popularly known at various parts of the country as *Ankola*, *Akhaul*, *Ankar kanta*, *Alagi*, *Ankolamu* etc., this species was formerly included⁵ in the N.O. *Cornaceae* but now considered⁷ to belong to a distinct monogeneric family, *Alangiaceae*. Besides being reputed for its use in the indigenous system of medicine as anthelmintic, purgative, alterative, emetic, in cases of bites from snakes and rabid animals, in leprosy, syphilis and a number of other diseases^{6, 8} it was reported to have

1. A. Chatterjee, S. C. Pakrashi and G. Werner in L. Zechmeister, *Fortschritte der Chemie organischer Naturstoffe*, Vol. XIII, pp. 346-443. Springer-Verlag, Vienna (1956).
2. S. C. Pakrashi and B. Achari, *Farmazia* (Russian): *J. Sci. industr. Res.*, in press; S. C. Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1960, 20, 77; *Ann. Vol. Physiol. Exptl. Med. Sci.*, 1960, 2, 97; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 587.
3. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, *Indian Medicinal Plants*, 2nd ed. Vol. II, p. 1236. L. M. Basu, Allahabad, India (1935).
4. B. L. Manjunath, *The Wealth of India—Raw materials*, Vol. I, p. 42. Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, Delhi (1948).
5. R. N. Chopra, I. C. Chopra, K. L. Handa and L. D. Kapur, *Indigenous Drugs of India*, 2nd ed. p. 270, U. N. Dhur & Sons, Calcutta (1958).
6. J. D. Hooker, *The Flora of British India*, Vol. II, p. 740. L. Reeve & Co. Ltd., Kent (1879).
7. N. L. Bor, *Manual of Indian Forest Botany*, 1st ed., p. 99. Oxford University Press, Oxford (1953).

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hypotensive properties. Chopra and Chowhan⁸ observed that an alkaloidal principle from its root-bark produced a slow but sustained hypotension in cat as a parasympathetic stimulant while Raymond-Hamet⁹ reported similar activity of aqueous extract thereof in chloralosed dogs.

We also observed¹⁰⁻¹² that an amorphous alkaloid mixture, AL 60, m.p. 160-62°, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$: 0°, isolated by us from the steam-bark and now being chemically investigated, produces interesting biphasic action on blood pressure depending on dose level. The drug recorded a rise at doses 0.1 to 0.2 mg/kg, i.v. and at still higher dosage (0.8-1.6 mg/kg, i.v.) it depressed the blood pressure of cat to the extent of 20-30 mm of Hg. The action was prolonged and sustained in each case. It has a low toxicity (LD₅₀, 75 mg/kg, i.v.) and very little, if any, undesirable side effects. Detailed studies¹² on the mechanism of action revealed that while the hypertensive activity is mainly of central origin, both central and peripheral activities must be operative for the hypotensive response. The total seed alkaloids exhibited^{13,14} similar effects. The drug behaved as an adrenergic blocking agent in general.

The potentiality of yet another indigenous source for the prevention of blood pressure disorders led us to undertake the thorough investigation of this plant. Though chemical work by the majority of earlier workers (vide infra) could not be substantiated, unexpected and interesting results were obtained leading to the breakthrough in this hitherto unresolved problem.

The alkaloids: Chopra and Chowhan⁸ who appear to initiate the systematic investigation on this plant, reported in 1934 the isolation of a yellow, amorphous alkaloid, alangine, m.p. 80-82°, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -34° (CHCl₃) from the root-bark of *A. lanurckii*, though a reference to an alkaloid of the same name and from the same source is traceable in the old literature¹⁵. Isolation of a number of alkaloids from the root-bark (Table I) has since been claimed¹⁶⁻²⁰. The questionable homogeneity, hardly reproducible isolation procedures, incomplete data and inconsistent naming of alkaloids left the literature in a state of utter confusion when we undertook the investigation in this field. It will be apparent from the

8. R. N. Chopra and J. S. Chowhan, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1934, **21**, 507.
9. Raymond-Hamet, *Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1941, **135**, 1011; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1945, **39**, 1929.
10. A. K. Dutta and S. C. Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1960, **20**, 279.
11. A. K. Dutta and S. C. Pakrashi, *ibid.*, 1961, **21**, 109.
12. A. K. Dutta and S. C. Pakrashi, *ibid.*, 1962, **22**, 129.
13. A. K. Dutta and S. C. Pakrashi, *ibid.*, 1962, **22**, 23.
14. A. K. Dutta and S. C. Pakrashi, *ibid.*, 1963, **23**, 285.
15. W. Dymock, *Pharmacographia Indica*, Vol. 2, p. 164. Education Society Press, Bombay (1893).
16. D. B. Parihar and S. B. Dutt, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1946, **23A**, 325.
17. M. P. Singh and J. D. Tewari, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1948, **17A**, 1.
18. N. K. Basu, N. S. Nair and N. N. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1950, **12**, 98.
19. N. K. Basu and K. D. Gode, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 629.
20. J. S. Bhakuni, M. M. Dhar and M. L. Dhar, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 8.

table that a number of alkaloids having close melting points were considered to be distinct compounds with same or different names, e.g. alangine of Chopra and Chowhan⁸ vs. alangine A of Bhakuni *et al*²⁰; alangine B of the latter workers vs alangine B of Singh and Tewari¹¹. Again, the same name was given to clearly different compounds, e.g. alangine A, m.p. 219-220° of Singh and Tewari and alangine A, m.p. 85° of Bhakuni *et al.*; alangine. m.p. 80-82° of Chopra and Chowhan⁸ vs alangine, m.p. 205-208° of Parihar and Dutt¹⁰.

TABLE I

Alkaloids claimed to have been isolated from the root-bark of Alangium lamarckii Thw., by earlier workers.

Sl. No.	Name of alkaloid	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Reported by
1.	Alangine	—	80- 82	Chopra & Chowhan ⁸
2.	Alangine	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ NO ₇	205-208	Parihar & Dutt ¹⁰
3.	Alangine A	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₇ O ₅	219-220	Singh & Tewari ¹¹
4.	Alangine B	—	105-107	-do-
5.	Alanginine	—	245-247	-do-
6.	Akharkantine	—	146-148	Basu, Nair & Bhattacharya ²¹
7.	Ankoline	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	110	-do-
8.	Lamarckine	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N ₇ O ₄	60- 62	-do-
9.	Base B ₁	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ NO ₅	197-198	Basu & Gode ²²
10.	Base B ₂	C ₂₇ H ₃₄ NO ₅	119-120	-do-
11.	Base B ₃	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ NO ₄	160-161	-do-
12.	Base B ₄	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ NO ₇	149-150	-do-
13.	Base B ₅	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ NO ₅	177-179	-do-
14.	Alangine A	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ NO ₇	85	Bhakuni, Dhar & Dhar ²⁰
15.	Alangine B	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ NO ₅	107-108	-do-

Besides, unavailability of the samples from workers who reported to have isolated them, amorphous nature as well as the heat and photo sensitivity of the phenolic bases and their derivatives rendered the initial phase of our work extremely difficult. No structural information was available either except the 3-anisyl-2-piperidyl-n-propanol (I) structure proposed by Bhakuni, Dhar and Dhar²⁰ for alangine A which we disproved by synthesis²¹.

21. S. C. Pakrashi and S. K. Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 923; see however, R. S. Kapil, D. S. Bhakuni, Nitya Anand and M. L. Dhar, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 136.

We first selected alamarckine, a well-known crystalline N-methyl derivative, m.p. 190-91°, of the total amorphous alkaloids reported by Subbaratnam and Siddiqui²² for structural studies since we had little difficulty in isolating this compound by slight modification of the original procedure.

FIG. 1.

The application of mass spectrometry not only led to the correct formula, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$, revised from $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ but also unexpectedly revealed the identity of alamarckine with N-methylcephaeline (II) guessed from physical constants. Eventually cephaeline (III), psychotrine (IV) and emetine (V) could be isolated from the seeds²³, as well as root-bark²⁴. Incidentally, we also suggested the identity of cephaeline with alangine B of Bhakuni *et al.*²⁰ and probably of Singh and Tewari¹⁷.

The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of this class of compounds was studied in detail^{25,26}. Their spectra are characterized by distinct molecular ions. peaks corresponding to $\text{M}-\text{CH}_3$, $\text{M}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ and common peaks at m/e 274.

22. A. V. Subbaratnam and S. Siddiqui, *J. Sci. industr. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 432.
23. H. Budzikiewicz, S. C. Pakrashi, H. Vorbrüggen, *Tetrahedron*, 1954, 20, 399.
24. S. C. Pakrashi and P. P. Ghosh-Dastidar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 379.
25. H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi and D. H. Williams, *Structure Elucidation of Natural Products by Mass Spectrometry*, Vol. I, (a) p. 184. (b) p. 222, Holden-Day, Inc., San Francisco (1964).

273, 192-190 originating from the common A|B|C ring system; the intensities of these peaks and the additional fragmentations are however dependent on the nature of unsaturation in ring D that allows differentiation between the different types²⁶.

It is pertinent to point out, that this was the first reported occurrence of Ipecac alkaloids in source other than *Ipecacuanha* (Rubiaceae). Though not rich in emetine content, a number of industrial methods are known²⁷ for the single step conversion of the major alkaloid cephaeline to emetine. Growing abundantly throughout the country with high alkaloidal content, *A. lamarckii* may thus prove to be a good substitute for *Ipecacuanha* and an important indigenous source of emetine. Significantly enough, an almost unnoticed observation¹⁰ made some 75 years ago by Dr. Mohideen Sheriff that the root-bark of *A. lamarckii* could safely be used as a substitute for *Ipecacuanha* for all diseases for which the latter is recommended except dysentery now becomes understandable.

From the resins separated during the isolation of the so-called ipecac alkaloids, we could isolate²⁸ a highly crystalline base, provisionally designated as AL 64, $C_{20}H_{27}N_3O_3$, m.p. 272°, $[\alpha]_D -64^\circ$ (CHCl₃) later proved^{29,30} to be identical with tubulosine, having a novel benzoquinolizidine-β-carboline hybrid structure (VI) initially encountered in *Pogonopus tubulosus* (DC) Schumann (Rubiaceae)³¹.

Since then two alkaloids, viz. desmethyltubulosine (VII)^{32,33} and isotubulosine (VIII)³⁴ have been reported from the same source. Recently, two more new phenolic alkaloids, namely, desmethylpsychotrine, $C_{27}H_{24}N_2O_5$, m.p. 166-68°, $[\alpha]_D +67.9^\circ$ (c. 0.50 MeOH) and alangicine, $C_{26}H_{26}N_2O_5$, m.p. 147-48°, $[\alpha]_D +64.1^\circ$ (c. 0.26 MeOH) closely associated with psychotrine have been isolated³³ in our laboratory.

Alangicine contains three methoxyl and two phenolic hydroxyl groups. The mass spectrum when compared with that of psychotrine showed that the fragments corresponding to the benzoquinolizidine moiety are shifted to higher values by 16 mass units while those for the isoquinoline residue (DE ring) remained unaltered. Evidently, the additional hydroxyl function must be located in ring A of psychotrine. In analogy with the structures of alangimarckine (XII) and ankorine

26. S. C. Pakrashi, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 1963, **35A**, (pt. 4), 465.

27. F. E. Hamerslag, *The Technology and Chemistry of Alkaloids*, p. 162. D. van Nostrand Co., New York (1950).

28. S. C. Pakrashi, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 468.

29. H. Monteiro, H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi, R. R. Arndt and W. H. Baarschers, *Chem. Comm.* (London), 1965, 317.

30. S. C. Pakrashi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1966, **35**, 468.

31. P. Brauchi, V. Deulofeu, H. Budzikiewicz and C. Djerassi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1895.

32. A. Popelak, E. Haack and H. Spingler, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 1081.

33. S. C. Pakrashi and E. Ali, *Ibid.*, 1967, 2143.

34. A. Popelak, E. Haack and H. Spingler, *Ibid.*, 1966, 5077.

(XIII)³⁵, the extra phenolic group was placed in position 8 and the tentative structure IX assigned to this alkaloid though the absolute stereochemistry remains yet to be settled.

FIG. 2.

Desmethylpsychotrine yielded O-methylpsychotrine on treatment with excess of diazomethane. On the other hand, psychotrine on mild demethylation furnished desmethylpsychotrine. The peaks corresponding to A|B|C ring system in the mass spectrum of the latter were found to be shifted to lower values by 14 mass units than those of the former. All these data led to the two alternative structures X or XI for desmethylpsychotrine.

Controlled methylation with diazomethane and the follow up of the progress of reaction by TLC at short intervals has shown that etheration at position 6' is more facile than in ring A whereas the observed ether cleavage in psychotrine is expected³⁶ preferentially at position 7. We thus favour structure XI for desmethylpsychotrine.

35. A. R. Battersby, R. S. Kapiř, D. S. Bhakuni, S. P. Popli, J. R. Merchant and S. S. Salgar, *ibid.*, 1966, 4968.

36. S. Teitel and A. Brossi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 4068.

Non-alkaloidal Constituents : As in the case of alkaloids, confusion prevailed as regards to the non-alkaloidal constituent present in *A. lamarckii*. Isolation of what appears to be the same compound from the seed kernels was reported simultaneously by two groups of workers^{37,38} as a sterol. While Bhargava and Dutta³⁷ assigned an unlikely formula, $C_{42}H_{84}O_7$, to their alangol (m.p. 296°), Lakshminarasimhaiah *et al.*³⁸ forwarded a more rational composition, $C_{30}H_{56}O_3$ to their alengol (m.p. 302–307°). A mono- and a di-acetate were also described. Salgar and Merchant³⁹ also recently claimed a sterol, m.p. 288–289°, from the fruits.

From the petroleum ether extract of the stem-bark, we separated⁴⁰ β -sitosterol and stigmasterol both in the free and combined states and an unidentified colourless compound, m.p. 128–129°. The only sterol encountered by us in the identical extract of seed kernels was β -sitosterol. We could however isolate the hitherto unreported betulinic acid (XIV), m.p. 306°, $[\alpha]_D +20^\circ$, betulinaldehyde (XV), m.p. 190°, $[\alpha]_D +19^\circ$, betulin (XVI)⁴¹, m.p. 254–256°, $[\gamma]_D +21^\circ$ and lupeol (XVII) showing remarkable biogenetic sequence, as well as lactone of betulinic acid⁴². Following the same method of isolation, it became apparent that the high melting sterol described by earlier workers^{37–39} is identical with betulinic acid⁴⁰. Betulinaldehyde has been rarely encountered in nature having been previously reported from only two *Platanus* species^{43,44}.

The lactone isolated⁴² was found to be identical with the hydroxy lactone A of betulinic acid (XVIIIa), $C_{32}H_{56}O_4$, m.p. > 320°, $[\alpha]_D +75.2^\circ$ prepared by Robertson *et al.*⁴⁵ by saponification of the acetyl lactone obtained either by treating betulinic acid itself with hydrogen bromide in acetic acid or its acetate with formic acid. The formate lactone however furnished a different product, hydroxy-lactone B (XVIIIb), m.p. 330°, $[\alpha]_D +59.5^\circ$.

In our attempt to prepare the acetate of betulinic acid with acetic acid : sulphuric acid : water (50:1:1), in addition to the expected monoacetate, the acetyl lactone obtained in 30% yield furnished hydroxylactone B on alkaline hydrolysis. The same lactone was also isolated⁴² by us from the neutral fraction. But it was probably an artefact presumably formed during the acid hydrolysis used in the separation process of betulinic acid since its presence in the original petroleum ether extract could not be detected⁴² by TLC. Further, we believe that the diacetate of alengol described by earlier workers³⁸ must in fact be a hydroxy-lactone of betulinic acid.

37. P. N. Bhargava and S. B. Dutt, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 16A, 328.

38. A. Lakshminarasimhaiah, B. L. Manjunath and B. S. Nagaraj, *J. Mysore Univ.*, 1942, 3B, 113.

39. S. S. Salgar and J. R. Merchant, *Curr. Sci.*, 1964, 83, 744.

40. S. K. Roy and S. C. Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1960, 20, 103.

41. S. C. Pakrashi, J. Bhattacharyya, S. Mookerjee and H. Vorbrüggen, *Abstr. Rec. Adv. Chem. Terpenoids*, p. 37, NCL, Poona, 1965.

42. S. C. Pakrashi, J. Bhattacharyya, S. Mookerjee, T. B. Samanta and H. Vorbrüggen, *Phytochemistry*, in press.

43. A. F. Thomas and J. M. Muller, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 1794.

44. R. T. Aplin, T. G. Halsall and T. Norin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 3269.

45. A. Robertson, G. Soliman and E. C. Owen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1267.

In order to ascertain the nature of the two hydroxylactones A and B, the common ketolactone resulting from their chromic acid oxidation was subjected to sodium borohydride and sodium-alcohol reductions when hydroxylactone B was obtained as the predominant product. This evidently showed⁴⁶ their epimeric nature and that the hydroxylactone B must have the more stable equatorial C_3 -OH function. Thus, epimerization at C_3 centre of betulinic acid at some stage must be envisaged to explain the formation of the two different hydroxylactones through acylation under different conditions. The study is not complete yet, but our recent observation⁴⁷ on the acid induced epimerization of arborinol (axial C_3 -OH) to isoarborinol (equatorial C_3 -OH) suggests the possibility of orientation of the C_3 -OH in betulinic acid being axial (α) rather than equatorial (β) as currently believed.

FIG. 3.

II. Studies on *Glycosmis arborea* (Roxb.) DC. (N.O. Rutaceae)

Glycosmis arborea, popularly known as *Ashvashakota*, *Ashshouru*, *Bon-nimbu* etc., is a common odourous shrub or small tree widely distributed throughout India. In the indigenous system of medicine, the whole plant or the different parts are prescribed⁴⁸ for anaemia, jaundice, rheumatism, cough, as febrifuge and vermifuge, in liver complaint, low fever, facial inflammation and as an antidote to snake-bite.

46. S. C. Pakrashi and T. B. Samanta, *Proc. 54th Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1967, pt. 3, 117.

47. S. C. Pakrashi and T. B. Samanta, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 3679.

48. B. N. Sastri, *The Wealth of India*, Vol. IV, p. 150, Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi (1956).

It was reported⁴⁹ that *Hortia arborea* Engl., a Brazilian plant of the same family known as an excellent stimulant and stomachic, contains a sedative and hypotensive principle, hortiamine (XIX) having indoloquinazolone structure. The analogous activity and the striking structural similarity with basic pentacyclic skeleton of reserpine or more closely to sempervirine (XIXa) prompted us to reinvestigate *G. arborea* from which arborine⁵⁰, a 4-quinazolone alkaloid having mild hypotensive action⁵¹ was already reported. Our initial objective was to ascertain whether this source might contain any indoloquinazolone or other simple quinazolones of interest for our structure-activity studies in relation to hypotension or of biogenetic significance.

FIG. 4.

Of the thirtyfive species of *Glycosmis* distributed in the tropical and sub-tropical parts of Asia and Australia, about eight occur in India⁴⁸. The knowledge of the genus is very imperfect and both taxonomy and nomenclature are complex.

49. I. J. Pachter, R. F. Raffauf, G. E. Ulliot and O. Ribeiro, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5187.
50. R. N. Chakravarti and S. C. Chakravarti, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1953, **18**, 539; A. Chatterjee and S. Ghosh Majumdar, *ibid.*, 1953, **18**, 604.
51. M. L. Chatterjee and M. S. De, *Bull. Cal. Sch. Trop. Med.*, 1960, **8**, 102.

Some confusion also prevailed⁵⁰ as regards to the identification of the local variety of *Glycosmis*. We have already recorded⁵² our reasons to believe that all the investigations carried out in Calcutta involved one and the same species which should correctly be designated as *Glycosmis arborea* (Roxb.) DC. Brizicky's recent elaborate treatment⁵³ leaves little scope for any further confusion⁵⁴ with *Glycosmis pentaphylla* DC. (and not (Retz) DC.). Govindachari *et al.*⁵⁵ recently studied the true variety of the latter (erroneously ascribed⁵³ to (Retz.) Correa). Our thorough examinations of the leaves of *Glycosmis arborea* led to the isolation of a number of hitherto unreported alkaloids and neutral components, the structures of all of which are now well-established.

The Alkaloids : We could confirm⁵⁶ the presence of arborinine⁵⁷, $C_{14}H_{15}NO_4$; m.p. 175–176° and establish⁵⁸ the structure as 1-hydroxy-2, 3-dimethoxy-10-methylacridone (RX). The U.V. absorption maxima at 395 (log ϵ 3.84), 274 (log ϵ 4.71) and 217 (log ϵ 4.38 $m\mu$) and IR in chloroform characterized by a series of sharp peaks were compatible with an acridone structure. The formation of the methyl ether, m.p. 167–168°, by refluxing with dimethyl sulphate in acetone in presence of potassium carbonate and not by diazomethane indicated a phenolic hydroxyl hydrogen bonded to a *peri* carbonyl.

The NMR (in $CDCl_3$ with TMS as internal standard) assignments (δ) which clarified the entire structure are shown in XX. The far downfield shift of the signal at $\delta = 8.23$ p.p.m. is quite characteristic of an aromatic proton *peri* to a carbonyl group that fairly eliminates the alternative structure XXI suggested by other workers⁵⁹. Because, the hydroxyl group in the latter is expected to shift the adjacent benzene ring proton signal towards upfield rather than lower field. However, it is not possible to rigorously eliminate the equilibrium between the two structures with the former (XX) predominating.

Incidentally, it represented the first reported acridine alkaloid in any plant indigenous to India and first unambiguous evidence of natural occurrence of arborinine⁵⁶.

The acridine alkaloids have always been found⁶⁰ to be associated with small amounts of furoquinoline bases. Besides skimmianine (XXII), $C_{14}H_{13}NO_4$, m.p. 176° reported by others⁶¹, we could isolate⁶² γ -fagarine (XXIII), $C_{13}H_{11}NO_3$.

52. S. C. Pakrashi and J. Bhattacharyya, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1963, **23**, 123.

53. G. K. Brizicky, *J. Arnold. Arbor.* (Harvard Univ.), 1962, **43**, 80.

54. D. P. Chakraborty, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 661.

55. T. R. Govindachari, B. R. Pai and P. S. Subramaniam, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, **22**, 3245.

56. S. C. Pakrashi, S. K. Roy, L. F. Johnson, T. George and C. Djerassi, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 464.

57. D. Chakravarti, R. N. Chakravarti and S. C. Chakravarti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3337.

58. S. K. Banerjee, D. Chakravarti, R. N. Chakravarti, H. M. Fales and D. L. Klayman, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **16**, 251.

59. S. C. Pakrashi and J. Bhattacharyya, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1965, **24**, 226.

60. S. C. Pakrashi, *Bull. Bot. Soc. Bengal*, 1964, **18**, 119.

61. A. Chatterjee and S. Ghosh Majumdar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2459.

62. S. C. Pakrashi and J. Bhattacharyya, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 49.

m.p. 142° but our deliberate search for dictamnine (XXIV), reportedly encountered⁶³ in the root proved to be futile. We have also shown⁶⁴ that glyborine reported by us⁶⁴ earlier was in fact a mixture of skimmianine and most probably arborikine.

More important from chemical and biogenetic point of view was the isolation^{65,66} and characterization⁶⁶ of three minor quinazolone alkaloids besides arborine⁶⁶ (=glycosine⁶⁷) which undoubtedly⁶⁶ exists in tautomeric forms XXVa and XXVb with the former predominating.

FIG. 5.

The three new members of the simple 4-quinazolone derivatives we encountered⁶⁵ were: (i) glycorine (XXVI), C₉H₉ON₂, m.p. 145-147°, a hygroscopic tertiary base, better characterized through its stable crystalline salts, viz.

63. D. P. Chakraborty and B. K. Barman, *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1961, 24, 121.

64. S. C. Pakrashi and S. K. Roy, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 187.

65. S. C. Pakrashi, J. Bhattacharyya, L. F. Johnson and H. Budzikiewicz, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1011.

66. D. Chakravarti, R. N. Chakravarti, L. A. Cohen, B. Dasgupta, S. Datta and H. K. Miller, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 17, 224.

67. A. Chatterjee and S. Ghosh Majumdar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2459.

B. HCl. m.p. 242° (dec.) or picrate, m.p. 249° (dec.). glycosmicine (XXVII), $C_9H_6O_2N_2$, m.p. 270°-271° and glycosminine⁶⁵ (=glycosmine⁶¹: XXVIII), m.p. 249°.

The complete structures of these three alkaloids and that they exist in equilibrium forms, a fact difficult to ascertain by chemical degradation and even by their syntheses which we carried out any way, were established through the combination of modern physical methods. It is neither possible nor necessary to detail the evidences^{65,67}, but it is certainly worthwhile to point out a few salient features of infra-red and mass spectral characteristics of this type of compounds.

A number of peaks in the region around $1400-1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($7.14-5.88\ \mu$) characterizes quinazolones and the interpretation of the spectra is by no means easy^{68,69}. We have been able to demonstrate^{63,66} with certain amount of confidence that two strong bands, one at $1626-1676\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($6.15-5.97\ \mu$) assignable to N-acyl carbonyl and the other at $1593-1625\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($6.28-6.15\ \mu$) to the entire conjugative system rather than any particular functions, e.g. $C=N$ in the molecule, may reasonably be regarded as characteristic of the 4-quinazolone system and those at 1650 cm^{-1} ($6.06\ \mu$) and 1704 cm^{-1} ($5.87\ \mu$) in the hydrochlorides of N-methylated compounds may result from the contribution of the mesomeric forms of the original bases stabilized by salt formation (e.g. XXIXa or XXIXb). This observation also receives support from the NMR spectrum. The shift of the signal of C_2 -proton from $\delta=8.25$ to $\delta=9.68$ and the methyl signal of $N-CH_3$ from $\delta=3.83$ to $\delta=4.08$ in the salt from that of the corresponding base clearly indicates XXIXb as the predominant form of glycorine hydrochloride. Further, a strong band in the region $1527-1566\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($6.55-6.39\ \mu$) is typical of only those N-substituted 4-quinazolones which are free from hydrogen bonding and that a band at around 1531 cm^{-1} ($6.53\ \mu$) cannot be ascribed to $C=N$ as proposed by Chakravarti *et al.*⁶⁰. We could also support⁶⁰ that the two bands at 1605 cm^{-1} ($6.23\ \mu$) and 1484 cm^{-1} ($6.74\ \mu$) typify a 2:4-quinazolidione system as observed by Culbertson *et al.*⁶⁴.

The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of simple quinazolones was found⁶⁶ to be dependent on the substituent at C_2 or N_1 and as such may be regarded as quite diagnostic of this class of compounds^{20,30,36}. For example, those with a benzyl substituent at C_2 irrespective of methyl substituent at N_1 (e.g., glycosminine, XXVIII and arborine, XXV) show a very strong M-1 peak apparently by splitting off a hydrogen from the benzyl function and subsequent rearrangement to the highly stabilized tropylium ion (XXX) while the molecular ion is the most intense

67a. S. C. Pakrashi and J. Bhattacharyya, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1965, 24, 293.

68. H. Culbertson, J. C. Decius and R. E. Christensen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4834.

one in others (e.g. glycorine, XXVI and glycosmicine, XXVII) without this grouping. Again, while the net primary fragmentation step of these quinazolones^{25, 26} involves expulsion of atoms 2 and 3 along with their substituents to yield species *a* further fragmentation depends on the presence or absence of a methyl at N₁ as would be evident from the conspicuous absence of the ion peaks corresponding to the characteristic species *b*–*d* of N₁-methylated quinazolones in the spectrum of the nor compound, glycosminine (XXVIII).

It is interesting to note that except two species of Saxifragaceae, Rutaceae family is the only known source of quinazolones of which *G. arborea* alone yields the majority of simple and a third of the total number of alkaloids of this class, glycorine being the simplest member encountered so far. To the best of our knowledge, glycosmicine represents the first isolation of this quinazolinone derivative from a natural source^{62, 63}.

FIG. 6.

The isolation of minor alkaloids from *G. arborea* is as significant biogenetically as that of simpler quinoline derivatives from *Angostura* bark that led Späth and Piki⁷⁰ to propose anthranilic acid as a probable biogenetic precursor for them. The biogenetic type syntheses of glycorine⁶⁰, glycosmicine⁶¹, glycosminine⁶⁵ and arborine⁶⁷ amply support Robinson's postulate⁷¹ that anthranilic acid (N-methyl-

69. S. C. Pakraishi and J. Bhattacharyya, *Tetrahedron*, in press.

70. E. Späth and J. Piki, *Ber*, 1929, 62, 2244; *Monatsh.*, 1930, 55, 352.

71. R. Robinson, *The Structural Relations of Natural Products*, p. 92. Clarendon Press, Oxford (1955).

lated where necessary), ammonia or amine and formic acid or phenyl acetic acid (derivable from phenylalanine) units or their equivalents build up the quinazolone alkaloids.

Although in any biogenetic scheme, the sequence of reactions is neither implied nor easily justifiable, our demethylation and remethylation experiments with a view to interrelating the quinazolone alkaloids from *G. arborea*⁷² led us to believe that where necessary methylation of anthranilic acid, the common precursor, or its amide precedes further condensation and cyclization. We observed that hydrochlorides of glycorine and arborine when heated above m.p.s. under vacuum were smoothly demethylated respectively to 4-quinazolone (XXXI) and glycosminine while remethylation of these products did not reform the original bases in appreciable amounts but yielded almost exclusively the expected 3-methyl derivatives. On the other hand, the naturally occurring quinazolones which more often than not are alkylated at N₁ are conveniently synthesized in good yields by prior methylation of anthranilamide.

A very significant observation was made⁷³ in our attempt to understand the probable mode of formation of glycosmicine (XXVII) which conceivably could arise either by oxidative fission of arborine (XXV) or from glycorine (XXVI) or dihydroglycorine by oxidation. We treated arborine with chromic acid in acetic acid under reflux for a brief period and quite unexpectedly isolated glycorine as the major product along with glycosmicine. Although oxidation of 4-quinazolone to benzoyleneurea (XXXII) presumably through covalent hydration peculiar to this system⁷² is known, glycosmicine might have resulted from the oxidative cleavage of the benzylidene form of arborine while the mechanism of glycorine formation is not yet clearly understood. However, it may not be unlikely that arborine, the major alkaloid from *G. arborea*, is initially formed in the plant and enzyme may mimic such oxidation to produce the other products in minor yields.

The metal hydride reduction of these alkaloids under various conditions also proved to be interesting. The results so far obtained⁷⁴ indicate that 4-quinazolones irrespective of substitution at position 2, with a free NH are very resistant while those N₁-methylated undergo facile reduction to their dihydro derivatives. A possible explanation could be that the reduction proceeds via a quaternary intermediate⁷⁴. Again, though facile reduction of the N-acylcarbonyl of indoloquinazolones by LAH has been reported⁷⁵, complete reduction of the same function has only been realized with the conversion of arborine to its tetrahydro derivative when treated with LAH under reflux⁷⁵.

72. St. v. Niementowski, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1356.

73. S. C. Pakrashi and J. Bhattacharyya, *Abstr. 3rd IUPAC Symp. Chem. Natl. Prod.*, p. 74. Kyoto, Japan, April 12-18, 1964.

74. P. S. Anderson and R. E. Lyle, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1964, 153.

75. I. J. Pachter, R. J. Mohrbacher and D. E. Zacharias, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 635.

We are interested in the field of quinazolones not only for their interesting chemical behaviour which is very uncertain and often unpredictable due to the tautomeric nature but also because it holds a great promise in the study of structure-action relationships and development of useful substitute for existing drugs of the kind. Besides the use of quinazolines in drug manufacture for their anti-malarial, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-cancer, fungicidal, bronchodilator and tranquilo-sedative activities, effectiveness against protozoan parasite (*Babesia canis*) and influenza virus, some quinazolone derivatives are important for agriculture as plant growth regulating substances and in dye-stuffs industry^{76,77}.

Neutral Components: From the petroleum ether extract of leaves, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, myricyl alcohol and two novel triterpene alcohols, viz. arborinol (=arborinol A), m.p. 274°, $[\alpha]_D + 34.2^\circ$ (CHCl_3) and isoarborinol (=arborinol B), m.p. 298–99°, $[\alpha]_D + 45^\circ$ (CHCl_3) were isolated^{78,79}. Both the triterpenes with the same molecular formula, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$, furnished on chromic acid oxidation a common ketone, arborinone, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$, m.p. 216°, $[\alpha]_D + 28.8^\circ$ (CHCl_3) thus proving the epimeric nature of the alcohols. This ketone on sodium borohydride reduction predominantly yielded isoarborinol establishing the stereochemistry of the hydroxyl function in these triterpenes corroborated by the usual treatment of the alcohols with phosphorus pentachloride⁷⁹. Arborinone has recently been isolated⁸⁰ from the same source. The co-occurrence of two epimeric triterpene alcohols with their common oxidation product is quite rare and is of considerable biogenetic importance.

Arborinone showed a negative Cotton effect quite rare for a pentacyclic triterpene with a 3-keto group⁸¹ and the mass spectral fragmentation pattern was markedly different from that of the usual α — or β -amyrin types in that *m/e* 205 peak for a 3-keto compound was replaced by a strong peak at *m/e* 257 (M-167).

Wolff-Kishner reduction of arborinone furnished arborene, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}$, different from all the known triterpene hydrocarbons. The unusual high m.p. 247° and the presence of trisubstituted double bond with two neighbouring allylic protons (NMR) indicated that it should either have a known pentacyclic triterpene skeleton with hitherto unknown stereochemistry or a completely new skeletal structure. By application of extensive chemical and physico chemical methods Vorbrüggen,

76. W.L.F. Armarego in A.R. Katritzky, *Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry*, Vol. I, p. 304. Academic Press, New York (1963).
77. A. H. Amin, D. R. Mehta and S. S. Samarth in K. J. Brunings, *Modern Concepts in the Relationship between Structure and Pharmacological Activity*, Vol. VII, p. 377. Pergamon Press, London (1963).
78. S. C. Pakrashi, S. K. Roy and J. Bhattacharyya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 651.
79. H. Vorbrüggen, S. C. Pakrashi and C. Djerassi, *Annalen*, 1963, 668, 57.
80. S. C. Pakrashi and P. Majumdar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 129.
81. C. Djerassi, J. Oslecki and W. Closson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 4587.

Pakrashi and Djerassi⁷⁰ showed it to be a new triterpene type and could establish the part structure with stereochemistry as depicted in XXXIII besides the presence of two secondary and one tertiary methyl groups in the molecule.

FIG. 7.

The complete structure and stereochemistry of arborinol have now been established as XXXIV by X-ray crystallographic studies^{82,83} of 2-bromoarborinolone.

We have recently observed⁴⁷ an interesting acid induced epimerization and rearrangement of arborinol. When left for seven days in glacial acetic acid : conc. sulphuric acid : water (50:1:1) at room temperature, isoarborinol, its acetate and two other products designated as isoarboronene-I, m.p. 187-190° and isoarboronene-II, m.p. 220°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +100^\circ$ (c, 0.5; py.) were obtained as minor products in addition to the expected arborinol acetate. To our knowledge the conversion of arborinol to isoarborinol is the first report of epimerization of an axial C_3 -OH group of a triterpene to the equatorial one under the condition used presumably through SN_1 mechanism.

82. O. Kennard, L. Riva di Sanseverino, C. Djerassi and H. Vorbrüggen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1965, 3433.

83. O. Kennard, L. Riva di Sanseverino and J. B. Rollet, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 131.

The mass spectra for both isoarbornene-I and isoarbornene-II showed molecular ion peak at m/e 408 corresponding to the formula $C_{20}H_{32}$ indicating them to be dehydro compounds. The other important common peaks at 326 (M-82), 255, 241 (M-167) and 191 clearly differentiated them from the already reported⁸⁴ Δ^8 -arbornene (XXXV), m.p. 244-245°. The relative intensities of characteristic ion peaks at M-167 and M-179 were compatible with a $\Delta^{9(11)}$ or Δ^8 , rather than Δ^7 -position of the double bond in both of them. Again, since unlike davallic acid (XXXVI)⁸⁴ with $14\beta, 13\alpha, 18\beta, 17\alpha$ configuration the rearrangement of $\Delta^{9(11)}$ double bond to Δ^8 , $\Delta^{12(14)}$, and Δ^{16} positions with concomitant methyl migration is prohibited⁸⁵ in arbornene series with $14\alpha, 13\beta, 18\alpha$ and 17β configuration (*cf.* lanosterol $\rightarrow$ isolanosterol). The possible structures for isoarbornene-I and isoarbornene-II are thus restricted to XXXVII-XL.

FIG. 8.

The chromic acid oxidation of isoarbornene-I furnished a single product. The UV maximum at $242 m\mu$ compatible with $\Delta^{9(11)}$ -12-one (XLI) justifies the assignment of structure XXXVII for isoarbornene-I. In conformity with the proposed structure, NMR shows the presence of only one vinyl proton. Under the same condition, isoarbornene-II yielded three different ketones clearly elimi-

84. K. Nakanishi, Y. Y. Lin, H. Kakimawa, H. Y. Hsu and H. C. Hsiu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1963, 1451.
85. D.H.R. Barton, J. F. McGhie, M. K. Prodhon and S. A. Knight, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 876.

nating structure XL. The one having $\lambda_{\max}$ at 240 $m\mu$ was not identical with XLI and could be accommodated in $\Delta^{8,9}$ -7-one (XLI) chromophore while those absorbing at 253 and 256 $m\mu$ are compatible with Δ^8 -7-one (XLIII) and Δ^8 -11-one (XLIV) structures respectively. The structure XXXIX can neither explain the formation of ketone absorbing at 240 $m\mu$ nor the observed mass spectral fragmentation pattern. Isoarboronene-II must then be represented by XXXVIII.

Unlike arborinol, isoarborinol with an equatorial C_3 -OH function formed only its acetate under the acetylating condition used. This is a little surprising since at least the 9(11)-double bond would be expected to shift to position 8. We propose to probe this question as soon as we isolate some more workable materials.

Studies on Structure-Activity Relationships.

In a series of papers⁸⁶⁻⁸⁹, we have recorded our attempts to correlate the hypotensive action of some *Rauwolfia* alkaloids¹ with their stereochemistry. But it is not possible to deal here with the detailed rationale behind this approach. Nevertheless, the more important aspects will briefly be discussed.

It is a common knowledge that both structure⁹⁰ and stereochemistry⁹¹ of a drug influence its action. In case of stereoisomers of structure-specific drugs, the nature and extent of biological activities depend on stereochemical factors that affect the availability and fit of the molecule at the specific receptor site⁹¹. Thus compounds with similar chemical structures⁹² and identical stereochemistry would be expected to exert similar drug-action and that the difference in activities of the isomers may be attributed, *inter alia*, to the nature of the drug-receptor combination and their adsorption at the complementary receptor surface⁹¹. Obviously, the relative and absolute configuration, conformation and steric factors must play very important roles on the pharmacological activities of fused ring systems with many asymmetric centres such as in yohimbine (XLV) and related alkaloids. The classical example of the activity of *l*-adrenaline while its *d*-variety is inactive, and the loss of tranquillizing property of reserpine (XLVI), with six asymmetric centres², in its C_{11} -epimer demonstrate the importance of stereochemical factor.

86. S. C. Pakrashi, *Abstr. 2nd IUPAC Symp. Chem. Natl. Prod.*, p. 83. Australia, August 15-25, 1960.
87. S. C. Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1960, 20, 309.
88. S. C. Pakrashi, *Proc. Hong Kong Univ. Jubilee Phytochem. Symp.*, (Ed. H. R. Arthur), p. 51. Hong Kong University Press, Hong Kong (1961).
89. S. C. Pakrashi, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1961, 21, 367.
90. G. M. Dyson and P. May in *May's Chemistry of Synthetic Drugs*, 5th ed., p. 37. Longmans, Green and Co., London (1959).
91. A. H. Beckett in E. Jucker, *Progress In Drug Research*, Vol. I, p. 455, Birkhauser Verlag, Basel (1959).
92. T. Sollmann, *A Manual of Pharmacology and its Applications to Therapeutics and Toxicology*, 8th ed., p. 46, W. B. Saunders Company, Philadelphia, U.S.A. (1957).

It is well-known that unlike reserpine, the other *Rauwolfia* alkaloids having the same basic skeletal structure of yohimbine or its close biogenetic variants are devoid of tranquillizing property but exert hypotensive effect differing in degree and sometimes in the site of action¹. Most striking is the regularity with which the activities of the known yohimbine stereoisomers vary as the configuration changes at one out of five asymmetric centres. It was realized that while the C₁₇-hydroxyl function irrespective of orientation hardly affects it, the configurations at all other centres have to be considered simultaneously to understand the nature and extent of pharmacological effect. A novel tentative correlation of the stereochemistry of yohimbine isomers with their hypotensive activity could thus be arrived at as follows :

FIG. 9.

In yohimbine class of compounds, the greater the number of *trans* relationship between the absolute configurations of the vicinal, physiologically important asymmetric centres (at C₃, C₁₅, C₂₀ and C₁₆), the weaker would be the hypotension due to sympatholytic activity only. With predominating *cis* relationship among them, both adrenergic and sympatholytic activities (adrenergic blocking activity) operate with corresponding enhancement of hypotension. If, however,

in any two isomers the number of *cis* and *trans* related centres become equal, the one with D|E-*cis* ring fusion would have more pronounced and prolonged activity. The latter condition is also necessary for the central action to develop.

This concept appeared to be applicable fairly well to other biogenetically allied alkaloids⁸⁷⁻⁹⁰. However, the absolute configuration of the C₁₀-methyl group in heteroyohimbine bases e.g. ajmalicine (XLVII) predicted⁸⁷ on the assumed correctness of the then knowledge of stereochemistry at other centres obviously needs reexamination in the light of revised⁹⁰ configurations at the D|E ring junction. Nevertheless, the marked hypotensive activity^{91,92} of sempervirine (XIXa) without any asymmetric centre clearly indicates that some part, if not the whole of basic skeletal structure is also responsible for developing hypotensive properties in this class of compounds while the stereochemistry may control the degree of activity.

The structure-action relationship of drugs is an intriguing and fascinating problem but the data in most cases are inadequate to arrive at rational conclusions which calls for extensive research.

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94. A. Le Hir, *Ann. Pharm. Fr.*, 1955, 18, 368.

95. D. Vincent and R. Lagreu, *Compt. rend. Soc. biol.*, 1951, 145, 348.